

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

NIH R15 Program Summary and Guide for Investigators

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP
Consultants Program

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About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution. The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

Summary

The purpose of the Academic Research Enhancement Award (AREA) and the Research Enhancement Award Program (REAP), collectively the R15 program, is to support small scale research grants at institutions that do not receive substantial funding from the National Institutes of Health (NIH), with an emphasis on providing biomedical research experiences for students, and enhancing the research environment at applicant institutions.

Quick Facts

For Institutions that are Undergraduate-Focused:

Title: Academic Research Enhancement Award (AREA)

Opportunity Number: PAR-24-152, PAR-24-214

Funder: National Institutes of Health (NIH)

Budget: \$375,000 in direct costs, for the entire project period

Project Period: Up to 3 years

Due dates for new submissions:

February 25, June 25, October 25

AIDS-Related Applications: May 7, September 7, January 7

- and -

For Health Professional Schools and Graduate Schools:

Title: Research Enhancement Award Program (REAP)

Opportunity Number: PAR-19-134

Funder: National Institutes of Health (NIH)

Budget: \$375,000 in direct costs, for the entire project period

Project Period: Up to 3 years

Due dates for new submissions:

February 25, June 25, October 25

AIDS-Related Applications: May 7, September 7, January 7

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Look for these author notes throughout. They provide research development (RD) insights and best practices to help you submit a successful proposal/application.

Purpose

The R15 program has a three-fold purpose:

1. Support meritorious research at institutions without substantial NIH funding,
2. Expose students to research (primarily undergraduate students in the AREA and primarily graduate students in the REAP), and
3. Strengthen the research environment of the institution.

Background and Funding Trends

NIH award-making trends provide useful insights into the funding mechanism. Identifying investigators and institutions that have secured awards, participation levels by NIH institutes, the total number of awards, and funding success rates, can inform a Principal Investigator's (PI) decision-making.

Over the last five fiscal years (FYs 2020-2024), National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS) had the most R15 awards with 517 projects.

Figure 1: A breakdown of R15 awards by NIH Institutes and Centers (I/C) over the last five years (FYs 2020-2024)

As shown in **Figure 1**, although all NIH institutes and Centers participate in the R15 funding mechanism, **NIGMS** makes the most R15 awards, comprising more than one-third of all R15s awarded, despite only participating in the AREA program.

NIGMS is likely the most common funder because most eligible institutions and investigators are typically pursuing basic science that fits firmly within the research priorities of NIGMS.

As shown in **Table 2**, the success rate of R15 proposals is moderately high:

- The overall success rate for NIH R15 proposals in 2023 was 26% (higher than the 19% success rate for NIH R01 proposals).
- Success rates varied greatly between NIH institutes.

NIGMS may be the natural home for many projects. Don't be tempted to target specific institutes because of high success rates. Contact the NIH program officer to confirm the fit of the project with each institute's funding priorities. NIH institutes not listed in this table participate in the R15 mechanism but have not yet made R15 awards, so if you are interested in applying to one that is not on the list, reach out to a Program Officer for more information. See the Submission Strategy section of this document for broader strategies for reaching out to specific I/Cs.

Eligibility

AREA and REAP have eligibility criteria for both the institution and the investigator. To be successful, both the institution and investigator must meet the criteria.

Institutional Eligibility:

R15 Eligibility Decision Tree

This decision tree is taken from the NIH site (see resources section for link). Your Office of Sponsored Programs should be able to help you gather the data for institutional eligibility. If reaching out to the Office of Sponsored Programs is not feasible, you can determine eligibility from the NIH RePORTER and Excel Pivot tables. The link to this resource is also listed in the Resources section.

Table 2. NIH R15 Proposals and Awards in FY2023* from NIH RePORTER

NIH Institute	Proposals Submitted	Proposals Awarded	Success Rate
National Center Institute (NCI)	138	20	14.5%
National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NHLBI)	77	22	28.6%
National Institute of Dental and Craniofacial Research (NIDCR)	5	3	60.0%
National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK)	26	7	26.9%
National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS)	55	12	21.8%
National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID)	106	21	19.8%
National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS)	161	74	46.0%
Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD)	76	23	30.3%
National Eye Institute (NEI)	16	6	37.5%
National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS)	25	9	36.0%
National Institute on Aging (NIA)	64	6	9.4%
National Institute of Arthritis and Musculoskeletal and Skin Diseases (NIAMS)	29	4	13.8%
National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders (NIDCD)	17	6	35.3%
National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH)	41	9	22.0%
National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA)	28	6	21.4%
National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (NIAAA)	8	2	25.0%
National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI)	3	2	66.7%
National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering (NIBIB)	26	8	30.8%

*Most recent data at time of writing

AREA Investigator Eligibility: A Principal Investigator (PI) must have a primary appointment at the R15-eligible organization:

- Each PD/PI must have a primary appointment at a non-health professional school or college within the applicant organization. If proposing multiple PD(s)/PI(s), each PD/PI must be at an AREA-eligible organization.
- The PI may not be the PI of an active NIH research grant at the time of a R15 award, though he or she may be one of the Key Personnel for an active NIH grant held by another PD/PI.
- Instrumentation awards (S10), conference grants (R13), and institutional training grants (T32) are examples of grants that are not considered research grants.
- The PI may not be awarded more than one R15 grant at a time.
- Eligibility restrictions only apply to the PI and Multiple PIs, not to collaborators, consultants, or subawardees.

AREA and REAP are ideal places for a PI's first proposal as the lead. R15 awards are intended to increase funding for institutions not traditionally NIH-heavy in their funding portfolio.

REAP Investigator Eligibility:

- Each PD/PI must have a primary appointment at a health professional or graduate school or college within the applicant organization, If proposing multiple PD(s)/PI(s), each PD/PI must be at a REAP-eligible organization; and
- Other eligibility requirements of AREA apply as well.

Allowed and Typical Activities

Research involving students is the highest priority of the R15 program. Students must form the largest part of the research team. Students must be compensated commensurate with rates at your institution, but stipends are not considered an allowable form of compensation. Student housing for summer participants is a permitted budget item but must be well-justified. Some institutions will also offer tuition remission for graduate students as part of their compensation.

The [Council on Undergraduate Research](#) has a wealth of resources on mentoring and managing undergraduate students. The number of students that can be supported by this grant will depend on their rate of pay, the number of hours they work each week and other project costs. You should think about the number of students you can offer high-quality mentorship, as well as how much work will be required to complete the project tasks. For AREA awards, it is increasingly unlikely that NIH will fund graduate students: the priority is for undergraduates. If a graduate student is included, there must be more undergraduates than graduate students on the budget.

Budget Considerations

Contact your office of sponsored programs to discuss your budget needs. They will be able to help you understand fringe benefit rates, student compensation and indirect costs. You should familiarize yourself with [allowable costs](#).

The R15 mechanism requires that the costs for the whole project are entered into the Year 1 budget. If your budget request is less than \$250,000, you will submit a [modular budget](#), which means you will round your request to the nearest \$25,000 and will not need to provide budget details. Note however that you will need to know your budget breakdown to calculate indirect costs.

Data Management and Sharing

NIH allows costs associated with data management and sharing to be included in your budget. Many disciplinary data repositories are free, so these costs must be well justified. In addition, you need to demonstrate you will be able to share your data long after your grant ends, so depositing data in a well-supported disciplinary repository is highly beneficial.

Dissemination Costs

You may include travel to conferences and page charges or open access fees for journals that are part of your dissemination strategy. You can include costs for your students to attend conferences as well.

Equipment

It is expected that the PI will have access to the equipment and resources necessary to conduct the proposed research. While equipment is technically an allowable expense, the limited budget for R15 will not support purchasing large pieces of equipment.

Unique Features and Special Sections

The R15 program has a few features and components that are not standard in other R mechanisms:

Student Involvement on the Research Team: The application must include undergraduate and/or graduate students on their research team, appropriate to accomplish the specific aims and to make an important scientific contribution. While NIH awards can and do often include students, most Notices of Funding Opportunity (NOFOs) do not require that they do so. The R15 does.

Institutional Letter: The applicant must provide a signed letter from the Provost or similar official with organization-wide responsibility verifying the eligibility of the applicant organization at the time of application submission.

Your library likely has experts in data repositories and curation. Seek out their advice for how to meet the NIH data sharing requirement with the greatest sustainability and lowest cost. If your library does not have such a staff member, seek out a data librarian at a nearby research intensive institution.

Application Review

Applications will be evaluated for scientific and technical merit by (an) appropriate Scientific Review Group(s) convened by the Center for Scientific Review, in accordance with [NIH peer review policy and procedures](#), using the stated [review criteria](#).

For due dates after January 25, 2025, NIH will utilize the [Simplified Framework for NIH Peer Review](#) as the standard review criteria.

Factor 1: Importance of Research considers significance and innovation. Significance assesses whether the application addresses an important knowledge gap in the field, solves a critical problem, or creates a valuable conceptual or technical advance. Innovation refers to the extent to which a project applies novel concepts, methods, or technologies or uses existing concepts, methods, and technologies in novel ways, to enhance the overall impact of the project. Factor 1 is assigned a score from 1 to 9; 1 is the best and highest score.

- **Specific to R15s, reviewers will assess** whether the AREA or REAP grant will have a substantial effect on the applicant institution in terms of strengthening the research environment and [engaging students in a meaningful research experience](#). Although not required, are the approaches to engaging students in research particularly innovative?

Factor 2: Rigor and Feasibility considers the approach, including rigor and feasibility. Approach refers to the likelihood of generating compelling, reproducible findings (rigor) and whether the proposed research can be done well and within the proposed timeframes (feasibility). Factor 2 is assigned a score from 1 to 9; 1 is the best and highest score.

- **Specific to R15s, reviewers will also assess whether** plans for engaging students in meaningful aspects of the research are clearly outlined in the experimental plan.

Factor 3: Expertise and Resources considers the investigator and the environment. It assesses whether the PI has the background, training, and expertise, appropriate for their career stage, to conduct the proposed work (investigator). It also assesses whether the institutional resources can ensure the successful execution of the proposed work (environment). Factor 3 is not scored; it will be rated as “appropriate” or “needing additional expertise and/or resources”.

R15 applications are not compared to R01s or applications from institutions with large biomedical research portfolios. PIs should focus on proposing feasible approaches within the R15 budget limitations. For example, reviewers often expect only two specific aims for an R15 project.

Check out the resources on the simplified review criteria, NIH mock review panel and the R15 webinar to understand how NIH reviews these applications.

NIH likes to see strong mentoring activities. PIs might consider offering mentorship training for graduate students, postdocs or lab techs who would be working with undergraduates. If the PI's institution does not offer these, PIs can look to CIMER for these training opportunities. If [CIMER](#) mentorship training is not feasible as a budget item, you can approach NORDP for trained facilitators to conduct these trainings for an honorarium.

- **Specific to R15s, reviewers will assess, as part of the expertise criterion,** whether the PD(s)/PI(s) have suitable experience supervising and engaging students in research. This is best addressed in the biosketch, specifically in the personal statement.

- **Specific to R15s, reviewers will assess, as part of the resources criterion, all of the following:**
 - Does the application demonstrate the likely availability of undergraduate students to participate in the research project?
 - Does the application demonstrate appropriate plans to recruit students from diverse backgrounds including those from groups underrepresented in the biomedical research workforce (See [NOT-OD-22-019](#)) to participate in the research project?
 - Does the application demonstrate appropriate plans for informing students from groups underrepresented in the biomedical research workforce (See [NOT-OD-20-031](#)) of opportunities to participate in the research project?
 - Does the application provide sufficient evidence that students at the AREA-eligible institution/academic component have in the past and/or are likely in the future to pursue careers in the biomedical sciences? This information is typically presented in the Facilities and Other Resources section.

Reviewers may consider the following items but will not give criterion scores for these items; they will consider them in providing an overall impact score.

- Protections for Human Subjects
- Inclusion of Women, Minorities, and Individuals Across the Lifespan
- Vertebrate Animals
- Biohazards
- Resubmissions
- Renewals
- Revisions
- Applications from Foreign Organizations
- Select Agent Research
- Resource Sharing Plans
- Authentication of Key Biological and/or Chemical Resources
- Budget and Period of Support

Data about students' career paths in biomedical fields can be obtained from Institutional Research offices as well as Career Services. This can be represented in a table form and will be included in the Facilities sections. However, throughout the narrative, undergraduate recruitment, retention and engagement strategies should be highlighted appropriately. Gathering this information will take time, so reach out to these offices well in advance.

Submission Strategy

New Submissions

Once you have decided to apply to the R15 mechanism, you should choose the deadline by which you will apply. NIH accepts new R15 applications on the 25th of February, June and October each year¹.

Review takes about 7 months from submission, and it takes 6-8 months to prepare a competitive proposal, so you should start working on the proposal at least a year before you hope to start the project.

This doesn't mean you will spend 8 months writing. Preparing a proposal starts with setting intentions, gathering advice, securing resources, requesting feedback and many other tasks beyond drafting, revising and fine-tuning the narrative. Contact your Office of Sponsored Programs to learn about your institution's timelines and cycles.

Desired Start Date	Plan to apply by	Start planning your proposal by
April	Previous year June 25	January
July	Previous year October 25	April
September	February 25	Previous year September
December	February 25	Previous year September

NOTE: Funding start dates are not guaranteed and are often delayed by congressional funding allocations.

Resubmissions

If the original application is not funded, the reviewers' summary statement will include comments that provide important insights about needed changes/improvements. Consider [these helpful tips for digesting and analyzing](#) the summary statement:

1. Reread the summary statement 48-72 hours after an initial read;
2. Summarize reviewer comments and outline ideas for a possible response;
3. Discuss possible next steps with colleagues and the NIH Program Officer; and
4. Draft a list of changes you will make to your project plan

¹ If your project is related to HIV/AIDS, the review schedule is different. Please review the deadlines [here](#).

RESOURCES

1. R15 Notice of Funding Opportunity: <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/pa-files/PAR-24-214.html>
2. NIH RePORTER: <https://reporter.nih.gov/>
3. NIH Simplified Peer Review Criteria: <https://grants.nih.gov/policy/peer/simplifying-review/framework.htm>
4. NIH Sample applications: <https://www.niaid.nih.gov/grants-contracts/sample-applications#r15>
5. Tips After NIH Grant Review: <https://cadc.ucsf.edu/sites/g/files/tkssra881f/wysiwyg/files/After%20Your%20NIH%20Grant%20Review%20-%20Next%20Steps%20V5.pdf>
6. Decision Tree for eligibility: <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/funding/R15-Eligibility-Decision-Tree.pdf>
7. NIH resource to determine eligibility from NIH RePORTER: <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/funding/Determining-Organization-Funding-Levels-R15-Eligibility.pdf>
8. R15 Research Areas by IC: <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/funding/R15-Research-Areas-by-IC.htm>
9. NIH Samples (Provost letter stating eligibility, Biosketch personal statement, Facilities): <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/funding/r15.htm>
10. R15 Webinar 2023: <https://grants.nih.gov/learning-center/nih-research-enhancement-award-webinar>
11. NIH Mock review panel (study section): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gEQh49zyv4E>
12. New Review criteria resources: <https://grants.nih.gov/policy/peer/simplifying-review/resources.htm>
13. UToledo tipsheet <https://www.utoledo.edu/research/rsp/pdfs/r15-cheat-sheet.pdf>
14. NIH Standard Due Dates: <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/how-to-apply-application-guide/due-dates-and-submission-policies/due-dates.htm>
15. Help with Data Management and Sharing Plan <https://sharing.nih.gov/data-management-and-sharing-policy/planning-and-budgeting-for-data-management-and-sharing/writing-a-data-management-and-sharing-plan#after>

This suggested timeline follows best practices. It is possible to follow a shorter timeline, but you should devote more hours per week to the development process. The most important thing is to allow for feedback from colleagues.

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

DETERMINE ELIGIBILITY

8 months before

Carefully read the notice of funding opportunity (NOFO) and this resource to determine eligibility.

- Contact your sponsored programs office to determine institutional eligibility.
- Start a discussion with your dean or department chair if you intend to request course releases or other resources for this project

Review funding history and success rates and start planning your application.

- Use NIH RePORTER to review the funding history for these programs and to recheck success rates.
- Look for and sign up to participate in sponsor briefings.

To decide when to apply, consider your teaching, research, service and personal obligations.

Review the full application components and create a proposal development calendar with target completion dates for each component.

Begin to form your proposal team. Proposal writing is a team sport. As you plan for your project, identify the individuals and offices that may be able to help. Make a list of the following:

- Anyone at your institution involved in preparing or approving grant proposals, for example the director of Sponsored Programs or equivalent
- The person at your institution who will write the letter of eligibility
- Anyone in your institution who has received a R15, or any NIH research grant, in the past three to five years
- Individuals who possess key information you might need, for example the office of institutional research for student body composition data, or the student employment office for pay rates for research assistants

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

- Individuals inside or outside your institution who control key instruments or resources, for example a microscope, reagents, animal models, etc.
- Any colleagues who would be helpful collaborators, consultants or advisers for the project itself, especially individuals who bring expertise or resources to make the project more likely to succeed
- Anyone who is also applying for an R15 in the next year who could be an accountability partner or be able to exchange feedback

FULL APPLICATION CHECKLIST

1. Letter of eligibility
2. Project Summary/Abstract - 30 lines of text
3. Project Narrative - 3 sentences
4. Specific Aims
5. Research Strategy
6. Budget and Budget Justification
7. Facilities and Other Resources
8. Equipment
9. Data Management and Sharing Plan
10. Bibliography and References
11. Biosketches for all senior personnel

Additional application attachments that may be applicable

1. Introduction to Application (1 page maximum; For resubmission only)
2. Letters of Support
3. Multiple PD/PI Leadership Plan (if applicable)
4. Resource Sharing Plan
5. Consortium/Contractual Agreements
6. Authentication of Key Biological or Chemical Resources
7. Vertebrate Animals
8. Human Subjects

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

CREATE THE PLAN

7 months before

Begin planning the project and prepare to meet with an NIH program officer.

With your mentor(s) or trusted colleagues, discuss your ideas, considering the following:

- How will you incorporate students into the research program?
- How will this project provide students with a high-quality research experience focused on the execution, analysis, and reporting of the study?
- Can you do the majority of the proposed project? Can it be conducted at your institution?
- Will your institution provide the time and resources needed to conduct the proposed project?
- What is your institution's research capacity and culture?

As you plan your timeline, allow time to co-develop the research enhancement plan with your mentor(s) and request their letter(s) of support and biosketch(es).

6 months before

[Draft a specific aims page](#) and budget outline. The Specific Aims section of your application is more than a summary of your proposal. It is a convincing "elevator pitch" that invites the reader (reviewer) to advocate on your behalf for funding (Monte and Libby, 2018). The Specific Aims document is what you will include with your requests for feedback, advice, collaboration, resources, letters of support, and program officer appointments. It is a living document that you will revise as your research plan takes shape and your thinking about the problem evolves. As you compose the other sections of the proposal, make sure to update anything that needs to be changed in your Aims.

The budget outline is a sketch of the things you'll need to complete the project. At this stage, you don't need to know the exact costs, but you will want to think about salaries, funding for students, materials and supplies you may need, travel costs, fees for using specialized facilities or instruments, and so on. Your sponsored programs office can frequently assist with preparing a budget outline and filling the details of what things cost.

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

REVIEW WITH AN SRO

6 months before

Each study section has a Scientific Review Officer (SRO). As soon as you have a draft of your Specific Aims, you should **request an appointment** with an SRO. You might wish to speak to more than one if you need help deciding which group is the most appropriate for your project. As an alternative, you can also use the Center for Scientific Review's [Assisted Referral Tool \(ART\)](#). To use the ART, enter your proposed title and the text of your abstract and your Specific Aims. If your project involves animal subjects, make sure to check the "Animal Usage?" box at the upper right of the screen. The ART will then provide a list of relevant study sections in two groups: Strong, which indicates a stronger fit between your project and the indicated study section(s), and Possible, which indicates a more tentative fit. Consider sharing the proposed study sections with a mentor or a more experienced colleague and get their opinion about which one(s) might be most appropriate for your project.

Program Officers and SROs tend to have educational and work experience related to the FOA and are intimately familiar with the programs they manage. Use this opportunity to get some insights from the experts before you begin writing.

For more general questions about the R15 mechanism, choose [the appropriate officer](#) for the Institute to which you expect to submit. As noted above, the largest group of R15 applications are awarded by [NIGMS](#), but you should determine what is right for your project.

In reaching out to an SRO or R15 contact person, always send a polite email that includes your questions and availability for a phone conversation. Attach and reference your specific aims document. Make sure to include the document in a universally readable format (PDF is likely ok, LaTeX might not be)

Share your specific aims with the program officer and request a meeting to clarify/discuss:

- Questions you have about the funding opportunity announcement (FOA);
- How your proposed ideas align with their priorities;
- The feasibility and scope of your proposed idea;
- Key priorities or unwritten rules; and
- Tips or tricks from previous program experience or their subject matter expertise.

The strongest applications benefit from revisions and helpful feedback from colleagues. Allow at least three weeks to get feedback from your colleagues and sufficient time to revise and incorporate their suggestions.

Begin writing sections of the application that may require **multiple rounds of feedback and revision.**

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

WRITE AND COMPILE THE APPLICATION

4 months before

Request the following:

- Eligibility letter
- Letters of Support
- Existing descriptions of the facilities, resources, and equipment that will help you draft the Facilities and Other Resources/Equipment documents

It is advisable to provide a draft of the letters you are requesting.

2 months before

Send well-developed drafts of the research strategy, PEDP, and research enhancement plan to colleagues/mentor(s) and your research development professional about 6 to 8 weeks before the deadline.

Consider including a **graphic** that summarizes your proposal in our research strategy. A reviewer can use your graphic as a roadmap for your proposal. Make sure to include the key elements of the narrative. The example below can be adapted for your proposal. Make sure to include undergraduate engagement in the graphic.

You can use free icons from the [Noun Project](#) to use as symbols for your project components.

Need

Why do you want to do your research? Use metrics to quantify the need.

Vision

What do you want to do? What is your long term vision for your research? What are your short term goals (Aims)?

Approach

How do you plan to do it? How does it link back to your Aims and your goals?

Outcomes

How will you know you have succeeded? What is the social benefit directly resulting from your success?

PROPOSAL DEVELOPMENT TIMELINE

FINAL EDITS AND SUBMISSION

1 month before

Incorporate feedback and draft other application attachments (i.e. your biosketch, the budget and budget justification, data management plan, Facilities, and Other Resources/Equipment, etc.)

- To prepare your biosketch, visit the [SciENCv tool](#). If you have an updated [ORCID record](#), you can import relevant items into your NIH Biosketch.

2 weeks before

Submit the full application package to your Office of Sponsored Programs.

Your institution will have established norms or policies regarding submission deadlines. Given that there are many administrative steps and compliance reviews required for submission to NIH, you want to give your colleagues sufficient time to adhere to all the requirements and meet the NIH deadline.

TIMELINE: DESK GUIDE

	June	July	August	September	October	Nov.	Dec.	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	Sept.	October	November	December	
Target submission date: February																				
Target submission date: June																				
Target submission date: October																				
Determine eligibility and gather insights	✓																			
Create a proposal development calendar		✓																		
Draft specific aims and get feedback			✓																	
Meet with NIH Program Officer			✓																	
Begin writing research strategy			✓																	
Send drafts for review and request documentation															✓					
Incorporate feedback and draft attachments																				✓
Submit full package to sponsored office																				✓

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